

ISic1505

I.Sicily inscription 1505

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (pietra di Fuardo)

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Found by Orsi in 1928 in contr. Diana, reused in cover of stone sarcophagus no.8

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 2385

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334854

1. Φλαμενί-
2. [α]ς καὶ Αὐρη-
3. λίου Ἀντιόχ-
4. ου.
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645006

PHI 334854

Bibliography

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 746
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